

Oscillatory Characteristics of the B-Z System containing Malonic Acid. Effects of Salts and Organic Solvents

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Effects of neutral salts and some organic solvents on oscillatory characteristics of B-Z oscillating reaction system containing malonic acid have been investigated. Presence of small amounts of bromide and traces of chloride ions destroy oscillations but relatively larger quantities of salts like nitrate, sulphate and bisulphate are required for the same. The rate of oscillation has been found to increase in acetone and dioxane, while in dimethyl formamide it remains practically unaffected. Suitable explanations in terms of Field-Körös-Noyes (FKN) mechanism have been provided for the results.

THE characteristics of Belousov-Zhabotinskii (B-Z) oscillating reaction have been a subject of interest for many years¹⁻⁹. The infeasibility of oscillations in HCl, HNO₃ and HClO₄, and the inhibitory effects of chloride⁷, bromide^{8,9} and the effects of ethanol⁸ and acetone⁹ on the rates prompted us to examine the effects of some more anions, viz. sulphate, bisulphate, nitrate, bromide and chloride, and some organic solvents, viz. dimethyl formamide (DMF), dioxane (DO) and acetone (AC).

Experimental

Chemicals used were either of AnalaR or G. R. (E. Merck) grade; malonic acid was from Riedel De Haen A. G., Seelze-Hannover. The reaction vessel was used as cell with Pt and calomel electrodes and the fluctuations in Ce⁴⁺/Ce³⁺ potentials were recorded in a Omniscrite 500 (Digital Electronics, Bombay) strip chart electronic recorder.

Results and Discussion

Tables 1 and 2 present the summary of results while Fig. 1 gives some representative potential vs time curves. Na₂SO₄ increases the time period (T) of oscillation (non-linearly) but NaHSO₄ does not affect it. NaNO₃ on the other hand, decreases both T and the time of initiation (t_i). Increasing amount of NaBr decreases T continuously but t_i passes through a minimum except at a very large [Br⁻]. On the other hand, Cl⁻ in traces (≈ 10⁻⁶ M) decreases t_i and T and at 10⁻⁸ M stops oscillations (amplitude nearly vanishes). Such behaviour can be understood as follows. Kinetically, both t_i and T are to be affected if any component of the well known FKN mechanism⁸ of the B-Z reaction is

TABLE 1—EFFECTS OF SALTS ON OSCILLATION IN H₂SO₄.
[MA]=0.064 M, [BrO₃⁻]=0.044 M, [Ce^{IV}]=0.001 M, [H₂SO₄]=
8 N, Temp = 20°

Salt	Concn of salt M	t _i s	T s	Frequency (per h)
—	—	572.0 ^a	116.0 ^a	31.03 ^a
Na ₂ SO ₄	0.10	705.0	114.4	24.93
	0.30	480.0	153.0	23.54
	0.45	540.9	206.6	17.42
NaHSO ₄	0.1	528.0	116.0	31.03
	0.2	526.8	124.8	28.85
	0.3	535.2	134.4	26.79
	0.4	528.0	135.7	26.54
NaNO ₃	0.05	494.4	79.2	45.45
	0.10	488.0	78.2	45.98
	0.15	501.0	77.0	46.75
NaBr	4 × 10 ⁻⁶	560	95.3	37.78
	1 × 10 ⁻⁴	648	87.3	41.24
	1 × 10 ⁻³	528	82.0	43.90
NaCl	1 × 10 ⁻⁶	501.0	78.2	46.04
	1 × 10 ⁻⁵	570.0	92.0	39.13
	1 × 10 ⁻⁸	1219.8	79.8	45.23

^aUsing no additional salt

influenced by the presence of salts. Some components may be noted as (i) the autocatalytic Ce³⁺+BrO₃⁻ reaction, (ii) Ce⁴⁺+MA and (iii) Ce⁴⁺+BrMA reaction. Both Ce⁴⁺ and Ce³⁺ form a variety of complexes¹⁰ with SO₄²⁻ and HSO₄⁻ and lower the rate of oxidation of MA and other organic acids by Ce^{IV}¹¹⁻¹³. This will cause decreased production of Br⁻ through the reaction component,

The delay in the building up of the [Br⁻]_{crit} will, therefore, lead to an increased time period due to slower turnover from 'sequence A' to 'sequence B' of the FKN mechanism.

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Fig. 1. Potential vs time oscillatory curve for the system containing (A) $[MA]=0.064 M$, $[BrO_3^-]=0.044 M$, $[Ce^{IV}]=0.001 M$, $[H_2SO_4]=3 N$, Temp. = 20° , (B) same as in (A) with $[Na_2SO_4]=0.45 M$, and (C) same as in (A) with 10% DMF.

Neutral nitrate has poor ligand capacity and hence can not influence the Ce^{4+}/Ce^{3+} potential. Its effects on the oscillatory parameters can be understood in terms of primary salt-effect on the autocatalytic reaction (i) in which the rate limiting step is known⁹ to be

The rate constant (k) of an ionic reaction is given¹⁷ by

$$\log k = \log k_0 + 1.02 Z_A Z_B \sqrt{\mu} \quad (v)$$

where, Z_A and Z_B are the charges on the two ions and μ is the ionic strength. Considering the contribution of the added salts only towards μ , a linear decrease in the rate of oscillation (hence increase in T) with $\sqrt{\mu}$ would be expected. The observed decrease is not, however, linear. The influence of neutral salts on the kinetics of reaction (i) has not been reported so far to our knowledge but its general kinetic behaviour is known to be complicated, non-linear with no definite rate law⁹.

It is possible that SO_4^{2-} and HSO_4^- might also operate through similar salt-effect. It is difficult to analyse as to what extent they influence the

reaction (i) via equation (v) and reaction (iii) via complexation with Ce species. It is, however, interesting to note that the observed rate of oscillation decreases in the order, $NO_3^- \approx HSO_4^- < SO_4^{2-}$.

Br^- and Cl^- ions can interfere in several ways but thermodynamic considerations make themselves obvious. Two significant redox couples in B-Z reaction are BrO_3^-/Br^- and Ce^{4+}/Ce^{3+} with E° values 1.445 and 1.44 V, respectively¹⁸; normally these data are not in favour of reaction (i). At sufficiently low $[Br^-]$, however, the potential $E_{BrO_3^-/Br^-}$, by Nernst equation, may become large enough to oxidise Ce^{III} , which has been found so experimentally¹⁹. The oscillations are correspondingly observed with a very low $[Br^-]$. As $[Br^-]$ is increased, both t_1 and T are found to increase with decreasing $E_{BrO_3^-/Br^-}$.

Though $E_{Ce^{4+}/Ce^{3+}}$ in HCl solution is very low, the potential in H_2SO_4 medium will not decrease by small addition of Cl^- . The Cl^- is, therefore, supposed to interfere by interacting with BrO_2 or $HOBr$ or $HBrO_2$,

This is thermodynamically possible in view of the following E° values,

The one-electron process being faster than the two-electron process, the interaction with HOBr is more probable. The Cl_2 generated in the interaction has higher redox potential than Br_2 and hence can react with MA faster than Br_2 giving back Cl^- . This subsequently reacts with the oxybromine species and keeps the cycle going on and thereby prevents oscillations.

Effects of solvents: The following observations are significant: (i) oscillations are not possible in 100% DMF + H_2SO_4 medium, (ii) oscillations are not observed in any of the other pure solvents + H_2SO_4 , (iii) t_1 , T and amplitude are affected to different extents by the use of binary solvents, namely, DMF + water, DO + water and AC + water, and (iv) smooth oscillations are observed in mixed solvents in general and in DMF + water in particular (Fig. 1, Curve C). With the increase in percentage of DMF and DO (Table 2) both t_1 and T decrease. In case of AC, however, T decreases whereas t_1 increases. The decrease in T is more pronounced in case of AC and DO than that in DMF.

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF ORGANIC SOLVENTS ON OSCILLATION IN H_2SO_4

[MA] = 0.064 M, $[\text{BrO}_2^-] = 0.044 \text{ M}$, $[\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}] = 0.001 \text{ M}$, $[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4] = 3 \text{ N}$, Temp. = 20°

Solvent	Volume %	t_1 s	T s	Frequency (per h)
Water	100	572.0	116.0	31.03
Dimethyl formamide	10	522.4	108.0	33.83
	20	465.0	109.8	32.79
	30	440.8	111.6	32.26
	40	432.0	113.6	31.69
Acetone	5	618.97	81.6	44.12
	10	908.0	84.66	42.52
	20	1419.6	70.8	50.85
	30	1717.0	64	56.25
Dioxane	10	477.0	124	29.03
	20	324.0	100.2	35.93
	30	271.2	98	36.73
	40	216.0	78.9	45.63

Three factors are usually taken into account while considering the role of solvent: (i) dielectric

constant (d.c.), (ii) solvation of the reacting particles and (iii) effect of keto-enol equilibrium of the organic substrate. From the data (Table 1) it is difficult to correlate the decrease in T with the decrease in d.c. values. For example, the former decreases in the order, AC < DMF < DO (upto 20% composition) and in the order, AC < DO < DMF (beyond 20%); while the latter decreases in the order, DMF (38) < AC (20.7) < DO (2.207).

In the reaction component involving oxidation of MA with Ce^{IV} it may be mentioned that AC, when present as solvent, is also partly oxidised by Ce^{IV} making more of Ce^{III} available for its reaction with BrO_2^- . So it is not surprising if T decreases and t_1 increases. The decrease in t_1 and T values in case of DMF and DO can, however, be understood if we realise that the bromination of the active methylene compound (which is an important component of the oscillating reaction) occurs through electrophilic substitution by Br^+ ion. The Br^+ ion formed by electromeric effect will be solvated more in DMF compared to non-polar DO and less effectively compared to H_2O . Thus the greater $[\text{Br}^+]$ in DO will lead to faster bromination and correspondingly lower t_1 and T in the medium containing DO.

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